

Figure 1

**But not the
only way**

**To interact with outer system, to exchange information with outer system,
or induce relevance with outer system, means the observation has occurred.**

Figure 2

Figure 3

**Pattern shown on screen, only one kind of shadow.
To show how much certainty have behaved, also how much information have got.
Wave-particle duality, actually means different certainty.**

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Most of this kind of versions is like that:

Figure 9

Figure 10

Similar analysis process with previous one:

Pattern shown on screen....

Only a kind of shadow.

Wave or particle describe same nature...

No need struggling to find both.

And what we are pursuing...

And now, my better version:

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

Figure 19

Inertial system

I am

The center

Of the universe.

Will you believe that?

Figure 20

Figure 21

Figure 22

Conservative quantity, caused by initial acted and removed action, causes via accumulating in same direction, Symmetry quantity.

Figure 23

Causality is transmitted instantaneously.

Future is revealed in light-speed.

Time is driven by Energy.

When same Energy used, the shorter the sooner.

When one path revealed, the others disappeared.

Only the **soonest** way remain.

Figure 24

In flat space-time, this is the soonest way chosen to be shown to us.

But in curved space-time, the soonest way is not exclusive.

Every soonest way is possible.

But in double-slit experiments, it's not real curvature.

It's like one kind of artificial curvature...

Never absolute 0 **curvature** can be achieved, so always **probability**.

